

NONLINEAR FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF
UNIFORMLY LOADED GRP SANDWICH PANEL

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to describe the nonlinear response of highly stressed sandwich panels using large deflection and plasticity analyses. For this purpose, a rectangular sandwich panel subjected to a uniformly distributed pressure load is investigated. It is modelled as having rigid PVC foam core, fiber composite laminate faces, and a supporting fixed rigid frame. Three different finite element analyses are performed: fully linear analysis, a combination of linear material behavior and large deflection analysis, and nonlinear elastic-plastic material behavior and large deflection analysis. With this approach, the contribution of each nonlinearity is separated and illustrated. Effective stresses in the core, according to von Mises, and over-all deflection shapes are shown. It is observed that yielding cores significantly affect the relative stiffnesses of panels which differ by the fiber orientation of their faces only. From this phenomenon, it can be concluded that a designer's choice of fiber orientation in sandwich panels with yielding cores may be based on other criteria than analysis of sandwich panels with fully elastic cores would imply.

KEYWORDS: Nonlinear; Sandwich Construction; Finite Element Analysis; Core, Foam; Anisotropy.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, there has been an increasing utilization of the sandwich concept in marine applications. It is especially in hulls of boats up to 50 m in length that

sandwich panels are commonly found. Many of these are high-speed vessels subjected to extreme slamming loads (various military boats, passenger catamarans, rescue vehicles, etc.).

Guidelines for sandwich hull design have been given by Det norske Veritas [1], but more work remains to be done in determining the response of highly stressed panels. Extreme pressure loads against a hull can result in plastic core deformations and panel deflections of a magnitude that requires nonlinear geometric considerations (large deflection theory). In order to study effects of such high loads, Reichard [2] performed pressure tests of sandwich panel-frame combinations with overhangs. This was done as an attempt to simulate continuous hulls with bulk heads.

The finite element (FE) model described in this paper, is based on Reichard's test setup and is used to aid in illustrating and explaining the effects which can be expected from a test setup of the kind he has suggested.

Meyer-Piening [3] has given results of nonlinear FE calculations of sandwich panels with isotropic skins, but FE analysis of sandwich panels with orthotropic skins in which large deflection theory and nonlinear material behavior are included and separated, has not, according to the author's knowledge, previously been published.

2. THE MODEL

2.1 Problem Statement A 27.2 mm thick sandwich panel (25.4 mm core, 0.9 mm faces) rests on a frame (it is not attached and friction between the two is neglected). On the other side of the panel, a uniform static pressure load is applied, as shown in Figure 1.

The material properties of the rigid cellular PVC foam core are given in Table 1. The faces were made of triaxial ($0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ$) fiber composite laminates, see Table 2. Referring to the axis-system in Figure 1, panels with faces oriented with the 1-direction (0° fibers) along the x -axis (short span direction) are referred to as X-type. Likewise, the panels with the 1-direction (0° fibers) oriented along the y -axis (long span direction) are referred to as Y-type. Hence, the faces of the X- and Y-type panels are rotated 90° with respect to each other. They are otherwise identical. The core and faces were assumed perfectly bonded and the frame was assumed fixed and rigid.

2.2 Finite Element Model of the Panel The OASIS-ALADDIN system [4], which actually is a structural optimization package, was used as a pre-processor to generate the input data for the FE program ABAQUS [5]. Due to double symmetry, only a quarter of the panel was modelled, as shown in Figure 2. It was restrained from y -direction displacements along the symmetry x -axis, and x -direction displacements along the symmetry y -axis. The panel was modelled as a separate body (with separate nodes) restrained from penetrating the fixed rigid frame in the z -direction (gap conditions were used). Large deflections and plasticity were accounted for in the FE-calculations. Post-processing was performed with BASPL [6].

A separate beam was sliced out in the x -direction of the panel, as shown in Figure 1. It was analyzed by the FEM, also accounting for large deflections and plasticity. This simplified approach was introduced to aid in explaining the panel analysis and as simple check of the panel calculations - in the linear response range, the beam calculations can be verified by fundamental sandwich theory, see for instance Allen [7] and Plantema [8].

2.3 Modelling of the Nonlinear Core As a result of manufacturing techniques, foam core densities may vary significantly, [9] and [10], which in turn affect the stress-strain relations. A core with randomly varying properties cannot be simulated accurately, but a representative mean value may be used as an approximation for the core density.

For a general explanation of the mechanics of cellular materials, refer to Gibson and Ashby [11]. From tests [10] it is seen that uniaxial tensile and compressive moduli vary somewhat and that these are not related to the shear modulus by isotropic relations. These deviations are relatively small, though, and with the limitations in availability of material data, isotropy was assumed in this study. In this context, it may also be noted that the FE-program did not have a separate option for cellular materials. The isotropic material input for the program had to be given as uniaxial Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, although the typically critical sandwich core property is the shear modulus. As a whole, the above simplifications of the core behavior did introduce inaccuracies into the analysis. The extent of these were not evaluated, but one may speculate that they may be less significant than the variations in properties of a series of core specimens.

The FE program calculates the effective stress according to von Mises

$$\sigma_e = \left[\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_z^2 - \sigma_x \sigma_y - \sigma_y \sigma_z - \sigma_z \sigma_x + 3\tau_{xy}^2 + 3\tau_{yz}^2 + 3\tau_{zx}^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

A fully linear stress-strain relation is assumed until σ_e reaches a critical value σ_e^s . Beyond this point, a nonlinear stress-strain computation is performed. The input for this was unpublished nonlinear experimental data from the Department of Aeronautical Structures and Materials at RIT.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 General The results of this work, based on the above assumptions, are shown in Figures 3 - 6. In the pressure load versus deflection curves in Figure 3, FE deflection results are marked with solid dots, and lines connecting these are fitted curves. Deflection results obtained at point 2 are not plotted, as they show a very similar pattern of behavior to those obtained at point 1. In these same curves (Figure 3) the terminologies linear and nonlinear core refer to the simulation of linear elastic and elastic-plastic

core material behavior, respectively. The terminologies linear and nonlinear geometry refer to the use of small and large deflection theory, respectively.

3.2 Linear Elastic Core - Large Deflection Theory In order to separate the nonlinear geometric effects from the material nonlinearities, a version of the model was run in which the core was modelled as linear elastic, but large deflection analysis was used. The results of these calculations are plotted in Figure 3. When deflections from the nonlinear analyses are within the magnitude of the thickness of the panel, deflections from the linear analyses deviate from those of the nonlinear by as little as three and five percent, respectively. In this context it is noted that, in a similar analysis with a uniformly loaded sandwich panel, which differed in having clamped edges and other material and geometric properties, Meyer-Piening [3] concluded that linear analysis was "sufficiently accurate up to the thickness of the panel". In order to verify the large deflection routines of ABAQUS and proper use of these, a separate analysis was performed. Obtained deflections for a beam of homogenous and linear elastic material subjected to a distributed load were compared to results obtained by a different FE program (B-FEM), Bäcklund [12], yielding essentially identical results.

It is noted that the Y-panel consistently deviates more strongly from fully linear analysis than the X-panel does due to larger deflection experienced by the Y-panel.

3.3 Elastic-Plastic Core - Large Deflection Theory Finally, a completely nonlinear analysis was performed with physical (material) as well as geometric nonlinearities.

Referring to Figure 3, it is seen that a loss of stiffness is experienced as the core yields. Core failure occurs at loads slightly above those plotted. These, in turn, correspond to deflections of magnitudes which do not imply important stiffening contributions from nonlinear geometric effects. With a core of significantly higher density and/or reduced thickness, such effects can be expected to have greater influence.

Again, by inspection of Figure 3, it is seen that the superior stiffness of the X-panel in the linear range is lost at high loads. This cross-over effect is first seen at pressures of certain magnitudes near the frame, at point 3, and at higher loads even at the center of the panel. This cross-over effect implies that as the core of the X-panel begins to yield, it loses its stiffness more rapidly than the Y-panel does, eventually making it less stiff. The behavior can be explained by turning to the X-beam, Figure 3: It carries almost as much pressure as the X-panel does until its core reaches a critical stress level. Above this, little increase in the pressure can be tolerated, whereas the X-panel at this load level has some further load carrying capacity in directions other than only its x -direction (due to its $\pm 45^\circ$ -fibers). Thus, with a yielding core, it becomes essential to have stiffness in more than just one direction. The Y-panel has substantially greater stiffness in the y -direction than the X-panel has, consequently the Y-panel distributes the load advantageously when the core yields. This very same explanation can be deduced by inspection of Figure 4. It is seen that, near the frame, the region with isostress contours

of level C has moved further into the panel in the y-direction for the X-panel than it has for the Y-panel.

Figure 5 displays enlargements of the over-all deflection patterns at a load of 75 kPa (the same load that was used for the isostress contour figures). At this load, large regions of the core are yielding and the cross-over effect is seen at point 3 (Figure 3). Indeed, from Figure 5 it is seen that the deflection slope in the x-direction at region α is steeper for the X-panel than it is for the Y-panel. Figure 6 illustrates this cross-over effect more clearly at the somewhat higher load of 90 kPa, by an edge view of the longest span (symmetry y-axis).

4. CONCLUSIONS

With the geometric relations and materials simulated in this study, nonlinear geometric effects have little influence on the stiffness when central panel deflections are smaller than the thickness of the panel.

Failure due to plastic deformations in the core occur before nonlinear geometric effects become large. Nevertheless, if a core is thinner or more dense than the ones discussed here, the faces may exhibit substantial nonlinear geometric action before core failure.

A phenomenon, here named "cross-over effect", is used to explain that the basis for choice of lay-up of the faces in sandwich panels depend upon whether the core deformations are elastic-plastic or elastic only.

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7. BIOGRAPHY

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TABLE 1. CORE MATERIAL.

Rigid cellular PVC foam of thickness 25.4 mm, with approximate Poisson's ratio ν and Young's modulus E [10] from compression tests.

Product name	ν	E (MPa)	Density (kg/m^3)
Divinycell H-80	0.3	89.5	80

TABLE 2. FACE MATERIAL.

Triaxial ($0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ$) composite faces, each of thickness 0.9 mm.

Fiber direction	Weight ratio
0°	3/7
$+45^\circ$	2/7
-45°	2/7

Panel type	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
X-panel	20.1	10.3	6.7	0.1	0.2
Y-panel	10.3	20.1	6.7	0.2	0.1

Figure 1. Illustration of the simulated test setup - a sandwich panel resting on top of a fixed rigid frame. The three marked points represent positions at which deflections are calculated. All dimensions are in mm.

Figure 2. Schematic of the FE mesh.

Figure 3. Results of FE calculations at points 1 and 3.

Figure 4. Stress level contours, according to von Mises, in the core of panels subjected to a load of 75 kPa. (A) 0.55 MPa, yielding begins; (B) 0.80 MPa, stress level half the way between levels A and C - a substantial part of the strain comes from plastic deformation; (C) 1.05 MPa, the nonlinear material stress-strain curve flattens out - very little additional load can be carried by the core (failure occurs at 1.16 MPa).

Figure 5. Over-all deflection pattern of panels subjected to a load of 75 kPa. All deflections are amplified by a factor of 8.

Figure 6. Edge view of the long span symmetry axis of panels deflecting when subjected to a load of 90 kPa. All deflection are amplified by a factor of 8.